

A CONVERGENT MIXED-METHOD STUDY ON THE TEACHERS' PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SPECIAL EDUCATION (SPED) PROGRAM

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A Convergent Mixed-Method Study on the Teachers' Practices and Challenges in the Implementation of Special Education (SpEd) Program

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Abstract

This convergent mixed-method study identified and ranked the practices and challenges of teachers in the implementation of Special Education (SpEd) Program. This study was conducted at the five private SpEd schools in Iloilo City during the SY 2023-2024. The participants for the quantitative research were the twenty five (25) teachers in all schools. The five teachers were selected as interviewees to gather the qualitative data. The duly validated instrument was used to determine the rank of the practices and challenges. The quantitative analysis that utilized ranking revealed the identified top five practices: individualized instruction, differentiated instruction, collaborative teaching, multisensory instruction, and behavior management technique. These findings were justified through the interview results. The challenges identified among the practices were the lack of specialized training for teachers, limited resources, and diversity of needs. These challenges were both found in the quantitative and qualitative results and were addressed through collaboration, resourcefulness, and attendance in trainings on their own. Thus, the project Teacher Excellence Advancement Project (TEAP) was proposed to enhance the practices and to address the challenges.

Keywords: *challenges, implementation, practices and special education*

Introduction

This study is legally anchored on Republic Act No. 277, also known as the Magna Carta of Disabled Persons. This law ensures the protection and rights of and welfare of persons with disabilities, including their right to education. It promotes equal opportunities, full participation, and inclusion in society, including access to quality education.

Furthermore, this study is anchored in DepEd Order No. 88, s. 2010 known as the Policy the Policy Guidelines on the Implementation Special Education (SpEd) Program in Public and Private Basic Education Schools. This order provides guidelines for the implementation of SpEd programs and it covers the roles and

Manlapaz et al. (2014) explained that special education pertains to the array of teaching procedures, utilized equipment and materials, accessible settings, and other means designed to attend to the needs of students with learning differences, mental health issues, physical and developmental disabilities, and giftedness. He said that Special education was inferred from two provisions of the 1987 Philippine Constitution. Article II, Section 17 stipulates that the state must give priority to education, while Article XIV, Section 1 assures that this education be available to all: suitable steps must be taken. Chapter II of Title II of the Magna Carta for Disable Persons, RA 7277, posits some rules on special education in the Philippines. Sec. 12 mandates that the State shall take into consideration the special requirements of disabled persons in the formulation of educational policies and programs. In this regard, learning institutions are encouraged to take into account the special needs of persons with disabilities with respect to the use of school facilities, class schedules, physical education requirements, and other pertinent consideration. In particular, learning institutions are encouraged to provide "auxiliary services that will facilitate the learning process for persons with disabilities. Sec. 14 of RA 7277 states that the State shall establish, maintain and support complete, adequate and integrated system of special education for the visually impaired, hearing impaired, mentally retarded persons and other types of exceptional children in all regions of the country.

Many students with disabilities have failed to make sufficient progress in the general education classroom. Although general education teachers must be responsive to the needs of students with disabilities, effective instruction by special education teachers requires a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of students that facilitates the development of highly responsive, explicit, systematic instructional and behavioral interventions that support the success of these students. To ensure quality outcomes for students with disabilities, special education teachers should provide instruction that is evidence-based and highly responsive to these students' complex and varied needs. Special education teachers must be flexible problem solvers who not only have expertise in using highly effective practices, but also are proficient in monitoring the effectiveness of these practices with individual students and making decisions regarding changes in practice as needed.

Along the above given premises, the researchers as a SpEd teacher, a guidance counselor both a private and public school are interested to find out the practices and challenges of teachers in the implementation of Special and Inclusive education program in the private schools in Iloilo City for the school year 2023-2024. (a) What are the practices of teachers in the implementation of Special and Inclusive education program; (b) What are the challenges of teachers in the implementation (c) How do teachers address the challenges encountered through their practices in the implementation of the Special and inclusive education program?

This study assumed that the teachers practices would include instruction that is tailoring teaching methods to accommodate diverse

learning styles and abilities, developing personalized plans for students with special needs, creating an environment that foster the inclusion of students with diverse abilities, utilizing tools and devices to enhance learning experiences. The challenges might be due to insufficient resources and support staff, balancing the needs of students with diverse abilities in an inclusive setting, struggle with time constraints, establishing effective communication and collaboration with parents. With these practices, an enhancement program is needed to improve the practices to lessen the challenges.

The findings of the study would be of great help to readers and researchers in many aspects. The SpEd schools, heads, teachers, parents, and future researchers would be benefited through its novel and enriching findings and insights.

Methodology

This study used a mixed method research through convergent parallel design to combine the quantitative and qualitative data of the practices and challenges of teachers in the implementation of the SPED program.

In a quantitative method the respondents were the 25 teachers in 5 private SpEd schools in Iloilo City. Four (4) teachers from Child Wellness Integrated Learning; five (5) teachers from Leap of Faith Intervention Center; six (6) from Children Explore intervention and Learning Center; five (5) from St. Mary's Academy of Iloilo; and five (5) from Diakonia Intervention and Learning Center.

The data gathering instrument to measure the teachers' practices and challenges were developed by the researcher with the assistance of the adviser. These instruments were composed of a number of items to include the vital practices and challenges of SpEd teachers in implementing the program. These were submitted for validation. .

Copies of the instruments were distributed personally by the researcher, data were classified and tallied for analysis. The statistical tool was employed as frequency to determine the rank of the practices and challenges.

In a qualitative method, the participants were the five selected SpEd teachers from the private schools. These teachers must be bonafide teachers of SpEd schools for at least a year. They have the willingness to participate. They are willing to share their experiences regarding their problems, obstacles, or challenges being teachers of SpEd schools. They have time for the schedule of interview. They are honest and sincere in answering the interview questions.

To uphold confidentiality and respect for their privacy, the real names of the respondents have been transformed into terms emblematic of the core principles of Special Education. Each term — Equity, Inclusion, Empowerment, Advocacy, and Accessibility —serves as a poignant representation of the unwavering commitment, compassion, and resilience demonstrated by educators within this field.

The open-ended interview guide questions were used to gather the data or description of the participants' practices, challenges, and how/what are their action to address these (challenges) for them to ensure quality implementation of the special education programs. The interviews were audio-recorded with the participants' consent and transcribed verbatim for subsequent analysis.

The qualitative research used the thematic analysis to find out the teachers' experiences in the form of practices and challenges through interview transcripts. The answers were gathered from the participants of which the analysis followed: Familiarization, Coding, Generating themes, Reviewing themes, Defining and naming themes and Writing up. These steps were followed according to Caufield, (2022).

With separate analysis using the statistical tool frequency to determine the rank and thematic analysis after which they were compared to find out the result and draw conclusions.

Results and Discussion

In a quantitative phase of this study revealed the common practices of teachers in the implementation of SpEd program.

Table 1. *Teachers' Practices in the Implementation of SpEd program*

<i>Practices</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Individualized instruction	25	1
Differentiated Instruction	21	2
Collaborative Teaching	17	3
Multisensory Instruction	10	4
Behavior management Technique	8	5
Use of Visual Aids	7	6.5
Positive Reinforcement	7	6.5
Social Skills Development	4	8.5
Speech and Language Support	4	8.5
Transition Planning	3	10

As you can see the Table 1 reflects the survey result of the Teachers Practices in the Implementation of the program. The result of identified and ranked practices of SpEd teachers in the private schools implies that individualized instruction is prevalent. For private

schools, they consider this easy to utilize; they can arouse to the fullest the interest of the individual learner; dealing with one client gives satisfaction in terms of closeness and concentration.

In Qualitative Results based on the Interview of the SpEd Teachers regarding their Practices in the Implementation of the Program.

Figure 1. Teachers' Practices in the Implementation of SpEd Program

Using the Thematic Analysis as shown in the Figure 1 that was based on the responses of the interviewees, the practices revolved around the themes of individualized instruction, differentiated instruction, collaboration, use of visual aids, multisensory activities, behavior management, positive reinforcement, speech support, and transition planning.

Quantitative Result of the Challenges encountered by the Teachers in the Implementation of the program.

Table 2. Challenges Encountered by Teachers through the Practice of Individualized Instruction

Challenges	Frequency	Rank
Lack of Specialized Training	21	1
Limited Resources	17	2
Inclusive Curriculum Development	15	3
Inclusive Classroom Management	10	4
Diversity of Needs	8	5
Standardized Testing Pressures	7	6
Professional Development Opportunities	6	7
Time Constraints	5	8
Limited Collaborative Time	4	9
Inconsistent Support services	3	10

Shown in the Table 2 the Challenges encountered by teachers through the practice of individualized instruction. The finding teaches SpEd schools that in the practice of Individualized Instruction, though there is assurance of education, problems among teachers may arise like lack of specialized training to help them perform their roles accordingly.

Table 3. Challenges Encountered by Teachers through the Practice of Differentiated Instruction

Challenges	Frequency	Rank
Lack of Specialized Training	25,	1
Limited Resources	20	2
Inclusive Curriculum Development	18	3
Diversity of Needs	16	4
Inclusive Classroom Management	14	5
Standardized Testing Pressures	10	6
Professional Development Opportunities	9	7.5
Limited Collaboration Time	9	7.5
Time Constraints	7	9
Inconsistent Support Services	5	10

Shown in the Table 3 the Challenges encountered by teachers through the practice of differentiated instruction. The finding implies that in the differentiated instruction, still the problem of lack of specialized training for teachers exists.

Table 4. *Challenges Encountered by Teachers through the Practice of Collaborative Teaching*

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Limited Resources	25	1
Diversity of Needs	20	2
Inclusive Curriculum Development	15	3
Lack of Specialized Training	13	4
Time Constraints	10	5
Inclusive Classroom Management	9	6.5
Professional Development Opportunities	9	6.5
Standardized Testing Pressures	8	8
Limited Collaboration Time	6	9.5
Inconsistent Support Services	6	10

Shown in the Table 4 Challenges encountered by teachers through the practice of collaborative teaching. In using collaborative teaching, problems may exist notably. Limited resources is an evident problem. To work collaboratively, it needs to understand the nature of the people a teacher is working with. This will involve parents in particular who are more dependent on the school resources. If resources are limited, then working in team might be disrupted or sometimes may cause ineffective learning.

Table 5. *Challenges Encountered by Teachers through the Practice of Multisensory Instruction*

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Diversity of Needs	19	1
Lack of Specialized Training	12	2
Inclusive Curriculum Development	10	3
Inconsistent Support Services	8	4
Limited Resources	7	5
Inclusive Classroom Management	5	6
Professional Development Opportunities	5	7.5
Standard Testing Pressures	5	7.5
Time Constraints	4	9.5
Limited Collaboration Time	4	9.5

Shown in the Table 5 Challenges encountered by teachers through the practice of multisensory instruction. Result revealed that the problem of diversity of needs of the learners and the lack of specialized training for teachers exist.

Table 6. *Challenges Encountered by Teachers through the Practice of Behavior Management Technique*

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Inclusive Curriculum Development	23	1
Lack of Specialized Training	20	2
Limited Resources	17	3
Diversity of Needs	9	4i
Inclusive Classroom Management	7	5
Standardized Testing Pressures	6	6
Inconsistent Support Services	5	7.5
Professional Development Opportunities	5,	7.5
Time Constraints	4	9.5
Limited Classroom Collaboration Time	4	9.5

Shown in the Table 6 Challenges encountered by teachers through the practice of behavior management technique. Knowing the technique in behavior management of learners, lack of specialized training, inclusive development, and lack of limited resources become the prevalent problems of SpEd teachers.

As you can see in the Figure 2 it was the Qualitative result of the teachers' challenges in the implementation of the program. Based on the responses of the participants, the challenges encountered by SpEd teachers revolved on limited resources as met in the practice of individualized instruction, differentiated instruction, collaboration, multisensory activities, and behavior management. Another problem was the lack of specialized training for teachers as mentioned in the practice of individualized instruction, differentiated instruction, multisensory activities, and behavior management. In the practice of collaboration teaching, differentiated instruction, and multisensory activities, the teachers' problem was on the diversity of needs of the learners.

Figure 3. *The Challenges Encountered by Teachers in the Implementation of SpEd Program through the Practices*

Figure 3. *Addressing the Challenges Encountered Through the Practices of SpEd*

Figure 3 shows the result of how do SpEd teachers address the challenges they distinct themes emerged from the research data.

Sought Alternative Resources, Shared Resources, Collaboration with Educators, Experts, Therapist and Resourcefulness

A noteworthy theme emerged from participant interviews and survey analysis: the encounter in each practices and it three struggle with limited resources. This theme was based on the Interviews of the 5 Special Education Teacher frequently encountered in implementing the Individualized Instruction, Differentiated Instruction, Collaborative Teaching, Multisensory Activities and Behavior Management Technique, a sentiment further, supported by the quantitative data ranking that Limited Resources as one of the top challenge. To address this challenge teachers seek alternative resources, shared resources and demonstrating resourcefulness.

Advocate Professional Opportunities, Open Communication with Developmental Pedia, and Sought Assistance from School.

Through the pursuit of excellence in Teaching and implementing the Collaborative Teaching, Differentiated Instruction and Multisensory Activities practice. Along with this implementation teachers often encounter challenges and based on the open-ended interview of the 5 selected Special Education Teachers Diversity Needs emerged prominently as encountered challenge and supported by the survey result as one of the top 5 challenge. Despite the hurdle of the Diversity Needs educators embraced collaboration with educators, experts, therapist and colleagues and fostered open communication with developmental pedia.

Attend Training on her own, Collaboration with Colleagues.

In the endeavor to address the lacking of specialized training in implementing, the individualized instruction, multisensory activities, and behavior management practices, teachers pursued two key solutions gathered from the qualitative result and supported by the quantitative result. Firstly, some educators opted to attend training sessions independently and open collaboration with colleagues.

Conclusions

In rank order, the findings revealed the following the top five practices: individualized instruction, differentiated instruction, collaborative teaching, multisensory instruction, and behavioral management technique.

The qualitative results revealed that the practices revolved around the themes of individualized instruction, differentiated instruction, collaboration, use of visual aids, multisensory activities, behavior management, positive reinforcement, speech support, and transition

planning. These aligned with the findings as revealed in the survey of the, quantitative research.

In rank order, the findings revealed that the top challenges met in the identified practices were the lack of specialized training for teachers, limited resources, diversity needs of the learners, inclusive curriculum development, inclusive classroom management, standardized testing pressures, professional development opportunities, time constraints, limited collaboration time, and inconsistent support services.

The qualitative results revealed that the top three common challenges, to include limited resources, lack of specialized training for teachers, and diversity needs of learners. These findings aligned with the survey in the quantitative research.

The findings of this study relate the concepts and researches manifested in the review of literature in many ways.

In this study, the practices and challenges were identified in the quantitative research and evidently aligned with what were discovered in the qualitative research. The study is related to what Jones et al. (2017) stated that recognizing individual differences of the learners is a basic concept when teachers prepare to teach. According to Ranjeet (2018), there are other effective teaching strategies to be practiced aside from being mentioned in the present study. These strategies the use of multiple-scenario approach to develop lesson plans.; monitor and verify student responses to lessons; evaluate and adapt lessons and necessary; use peers to revise lesson plans and to develop ideas that might be applicable; develop and maintain a pool of mentors; keep a list of resources for teaching, lesson plans and professional development, set professional development, plan, track goals; develop or implement a system that allows for easy and comprehensive data collection to help monitor and adopt lessons; and gather tricks of the trade from fellow teachers, including those who do not teach special education.

The need for administrative support, and on-going training and professional development, and resources are the key factors for the successful implementation of the practices as stated by Chitiyo & May (2018). These are also mentioned in the present study.

Evans (2015) stated that paying attention to the needs of students from diverse groups including the equality analysis/impact assessment processes is a usual way of ensuring the considerations to inclusivity and accessibility. Equally, it is also important to consider the rights of the learners (Yusof and Ismael, 2020).

This study revealed that Lack of Specialized training is limited and one of a challenge presents in each practices. The researcher recommended the Project TEAP Teaching Excellence Advancement Project where it aims to enhance the professional practices of Special Education teachers in Iloilo City and Provinces. Ultimately leading to improved academic, social, and emotional outcomes for students with disabilities.

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